

ATTITUDE OF NURSES TOWARDS THE CARE OF ELDERLY PATIENTS IN SELECTED HEALTH CENTRES IN ILORIN METROPOLIS, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Ageing is one of the national phenomena common to all races globally. Elderly individuals are always seen as giving increased burden on families and societies because most of them are incapable of performing their activities of daily living independently. This study investigates the attitude of nurses towards the care of the elderly patients either at home and work environments and especially in a selected health centres in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. Sixty nurses were conveniently sampled for the study and the result showed differences in the nurses' attitudes in the care of the elderly, these differences were premised on their knowledge, gender, religion, age and experience in the profession. It is therefore recommended that there is an urgent need for Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria to introduce and design a curriculum for Gerontological nursing as a specialty course in Nursing Education to better the knowledge and care of the aged by the nurses.

KEYWORDS: attitude, bio-psychosocial changes ,disengagement theories, gender difference, gerontological nurses , senility,

INTRODUCTION

Ageing takes place within a global village. Of the total estimated world population of six billion, six hundred and fifteen million, eight hundred and fifty-two thousand and one hundred, there are over 704 million people aged 60 years and above in 2007, almost 500 million people worldwide were 65 years and older. By 2025, that total is projected to increase to 835 million and over. Rapid increase in the 65 and older population is occurring in developing countries which will see a jump of 87% by 2025 and 274% by 2050 (World Population Ageing, 2007).

The process of ageing differ from species to species and also demonstrate diversity from one human being to another. Some general statements can be made concerning the anticipated organ changes, however, no degrees of physiological changes, capacities and limitations will be found within a given age-group. The rate of ageing among different body systems within one individual may vary with one system showing marked declines while another may demonstrate no significant changes.

Ahmed, Kraft and Porter (1986) were of the view that the attitude of professional workers toward the elderly affects the type and quality of care provided by them and the attitude of these health professionals should be positive, warm and homely. Also, accurate knowledge and positive attitude are essentials while every doctor should be knowledgeable of the course of ageing irrespective of his or her specialty.

Purpose of the study

This study investigated nurses' attitude towards the care of the elderly patients in selected Health Centres in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Significance of the study

The findings of the study are to be used to improve and promote development of positive attitude of the nurses toward the care of the elderly in the selected Health Centres and other health care service centres

LITERATURE REVIEW

Older members of the society have always received some degree of attention and many historical writings depict both the positive and the negative attributes of growing old. Confucius' time expressed a direct correlation between one's age and the respect to which one was entitled. Taoism viewed old age as the epitome of life and the ancient Chinese believed that attaining old age was an accomplishment deserving the greatest honour. The early Egyptians, on the other hand, dreaded old age and experimented with a variety of potions and schemes to avoid.

Ancient Romans, according to descriptions, had limited respect for their elders, in the nations Rome conquered, the sick and the aged were customarily the first to be killed. The Bible is laced with a theme of respect for the aged, although early Christian writings did little to elevate their status. The Dark Ages were especially bleak for older persons, and the Middle Ages did not bring considerable improvement. A strong feeling for the superiority of youth occurred during medieval times, with uprising of sons against fathers. The art of this period also portrayed an uncomplimentary image of the aged, father time for example. The aged were also among the first to be hurt by famine and poverty and the last to benefit during better times.

Many gains made during the 18th and 19th centuries were lost because of the cruelties of the industrial revolution. While child's labour laws were developed to guard the frail lives of minors, the frail lives of the aged were left unprotected and those unable to meet industrial demands were placed at the mercy of their offspring or forced to beg on the streets for sustenance (Eliopoulos, 1987).

Ageing process is a phenomenon beginning with conception and terminating with death with many changes occurring during the intervening years. In later life the decline at most of the physical organs become evident, all of the series drop somewhat in their efficiency. Most obvious, perhaps is the gradual loss of accurate vision which related in the increasing use of glasses as man ages.

WHO (2004) asserted that globally 37 million people are blind, every 5 seconds, one person in the world goes blind, over 82% of the world's blindness are aged 50 or over and aged related cataract is responsible for 48% of the world's blindness which represents about 17.6 million people and it is estimated that 75% of all blindness is avoidable.

During ageing, lung capacity is reduced, hills cannot be climbed without getting out of breath, fatty deposits in blood vessels that builds up when people are young, may reduce the flow of blood to the heart and brain at old age and blood pressure tends to rise, although, these and many other changes vary greatly in individuals but decline is inevitable.

Erikson (1964) believes that ageing process results in feeling of either integrity or despair i.e. a person's ability to see his or her life as having been worthwhile. The past cannot be changed but it is possible to combine it with the present and feel contented with the outcome or by contrast, when life is seen as lacking in value which may result from a person's feeling that he or she has not achieved worthy goals. It can also result from loss of physical and mental functions or from social isolation and neglect. The man or woman, who remains in good health, enjoys economic security and feels wanted by others is unlikely to feel especially despairing about old age.

Ageing theories

Biological, psychological and sociological theories of ageing tend to focus on different aspects of the ageing process but do not necessarily contradict one another.

I. Biological and physiological perspectives

Kyriazis (1994) claims that the theories converge into two main camps viz :

1. Ageing is caused by factors that damage our body like radiation, toxic by-products of the metabolism random everyday damage and the genes that promote ageing and the damage is not repaired properly, this may be because of a lack of metabolic energy, hormone deficiencies, lack of genetic support and failure of immune system etc.

Eliopoulos (1987) said in an effort to explain biological ageing, theorists have explored many factors, internal and external to the human body. Such as (1) Genetic factors: Several theorists believe that people inherit a genetic programme that determines their specific life expectancy. Various studies have shown a positive relationship between parental age and filial life span. Genetic mutations also are thought to be responsible for ageing by causing organ decline.

2. Lipofuscin: Considerable interest has been given to the role in the ageing process of lipofuscin age pigments, a lipoprotein byproduct of metabolism that can only be seen under a fluorescent microscope. This insoluble material does not have any known function in the body, but for some reasons it does accumulate with age. The liver, heart, ovaries and neurons are the sites in which lipofuscin tends to accumulate. Although the purpose and significance of this age pigment are not clear at this point, there is a positive relationship between an individual's age and the amount of lipofuscin in the body.

3. Autoimmune reactions: Another fascinating group of theories postulated autoimmune reactions to be responsible for ageing. Simply stated, the host attacks its own kind. One of the reasons for this may be that the body perceives old, irregular cells as agents to attack. Another reason for this process could be related to a breakdown of the body's immunochemical memory system, which causes it to be sensitive to normal body constituents.

4. Collagen: This has been linked to the ageing process, here is a thought to be an increase in the amount of collagen and a loss of ground substance with age. Collagen may become cross-linked, rigid and less permeable. The higher density of the connective tissue may reduce the rate at which nutrients are deposited and waste removed, leading to a deterioration of collagen and consequent slowing of bodily processes. Excess collagen can be detected in old tissue but investigators are not able to determine if this is a causative factor or as a result of ageing.

5. Wear and Tear: Another theory attributes ageing to the wear and tear of the body as it performs its highly specialized functions over time. Like any complicated machine, the body will function less efficiently with prolonged use and numerous insults.

6. Stress: It has been demonstrated that stresses to the body can have adverse effects and lead to conditions such as gastric ulcers, heart attacks and thyroiditis.

7. Disease: Bacteria, fungi, viruses and other organisms are thought to be responsible for certain physiological changes during the ageing process. Interest in this theory has been stimulated by the fact that humans and animals have enjoyed longer life expectancies with the control or elimination of certain pathogens through immunization and the use of anti-microbial drugs.

8. Others include radiation, poor nutrition and environmental factors like harsh crowded living conditions, smoking and inhaling tobacco smoke and other air pollutants.

II. Psychosocial theories.

Psychological and social changes during the ageing process are closely united and they have a significant impact on each other.

1. Disengagement theory: This theory views ageing as a process whereby society and the individual gradually withdraw or disengage from each other to the mutual satisfaction and benefit of both. The benefit to individuals is that they can reflect and be centered on themselves, having being freed from societal rules. The value of this disengagement for society is that some orderly means are established for the transfer of power from the old to the young, making it possible for the society to continue functioning after its individual members have died (Cummings & Henry, 1961).

2. Activity theory: At the opposite pole from the disengagement theory, the activity theory (Harvinghust, 1993) proclaims that an older person should continue a middle aged lifestyle, denying the existence of old age as long as possible, and that the society should apply the same norms to old age as it does to middle age and not to advocate diminishing activity, interest and involvement as its members grow old. This theory suggests ways of

maintaining activity in the presence of multiple losses associated with the ageing process including substituting intellectual activities for physical activities when physical capacity is reduced, replacing the work role with other roles when retirement occurs, and establishing new friendships when old ones are lost (Harris, 1990).

III. Political-Economic Theory.

Fennel, Philipson and Evers (1988) suggested that political-economic theory is a study of the interactions between government, the economy and these group of people who may be defined socially as the poor or the old. Older people have come to be viewed as an intolerable burden on Western economies with demographic changes seeing as causing intolerable pressure on public spending. The State plays a large part in this, in that it determines the events of later life that creates dependence, poverty or isolation (Townsend, 1981).

The development of priorities and practices for health promotion for a nation are dependent upon the prevailing economic and cultural conditions hence, there are some fundamental requirements for the health of any individual such as income, shelter and food. These needs to form the basics, complimentary requests are information and knowledge about health factors and skills to promote health, supportive environments that enhance health and the opportunity for health choices.

Whatever the degree to which the elderly disengage, maintaining integrity or self esteem remains a central task. This must be done in the face of increasing physical losses, loss of job and social roles, loss of closest companions. It has been suggested that health for older people should encompass self responsibility for health, nutrition, exercise, stress management, interpersonal relationship and support, spiritual growth and self-actualization, accident and injury prevention, safe and moderate use of medication and alcohol, avoidance of smoking, self care required for chronic illness and accessing preventive health services (Bernard & Philipson, 1991).

Bernard and Philipson (1991) did suggest three ways older people may confront their losses that come with time by:

(a) Redirecting their energy to new roles and activities. Retirement needs not mean being thrown on the scrap heap, leisure activities, hobbies, study groups and volunteer work provides opportunities for a later life that can be as rewarding (b) Accepting life which involves being philosophical about failures and disappointments. Many people become more objective in their later years and can weigh their gains and losses in the perspective of time and (c) Developing a positive point of view about death. In a sense, this means the ability to confront death directly and adapting to death. Kubler-Rose (1969) suggested five stages of most obvious reactions to death as stages of denial and Isolation, Anger, Bargaining, Depression and Acceptance. She further said that in actual sense these stages may or may not exist and not rigidly departmentalized.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

A descriptive survey method was used for this study to investigate the attitude of Nurses to the care of elderly patients in a selected Health Centres in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Sample/Sampling Technique

60 qualified nurses were conveniently selected for the study at Alanamu and Pakata Basic Health Centres, in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. Each of the centres was allocated 30 participants for equal representation since the two health centres had equal nurses and capacities of sixty nurses each.

Data collection

Research instrument used for collection of data was a self-reporting questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire contained two sections i.e. Section A was on demography of the participants while Section B was on variables relating to the study. The participants were given five options in order to choose their best choices i.e. Strongly agree, Agree, Strongly disagree, Disagree and Undecided. It is a Likert Scale type. The participants were expected to spend about 30 minutes to respond to all the items in the questionnaire. The validity of the instrument was ascertained through content validity. A draft copy was made available to senior research Fellows and after necessary corrections made, final copies were produced for administration.

The reliability coefficient was determined by a test-re-test method with Cronbach's alpha co-efficient score of 0.84.

Ethical consideration

The officers-in-charge of the two selected study centres were officially written to by the researchers for official permission which was expressly granted by them and appointment dates were obtained to meet the nurses on duty, this was done when copies of the questionnaire were given to the available nurses after their informed consent was given while other copies were handed over to the officers-in-charge for the nurses on other shifts and those off duties and a specific date was given for the researchers in order to retrieve the remaining questionnaires.

It is of note that all the sixty copies of questionnaire were retrieved and suitable for analysis.

Data analysis

Simple percentages, frequency distribution, tables and t-tests statistics were used for the analysis of the data collated for the study.

RESULTS

In this section, the results of the four hypotheses tested were presented in Tables 1-4.

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant difference in the knowledge and attitude of the participants toward the care of the elderly patients.

Table 1: t-test analysis of male and female nurses

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-tab	P
Male	6	3.04	1.21	58	11.52	1.88	0.05
Female	54	21.26	3.62				

In testing the hypothesis, the subjects' means were analyzed (male = 3.04 and female = 21.26). The standard deviations were 1.21 and 3.62 respectively. The data was subjected to the t-test analysis and the results were observed as, $t = 11.52$, table value = 1.88 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, hypothesis was rejected. Hence, knowledge and attitude of the participants are significant to the care of the elderly patients.

Hypothesis 2: Religion will make a significant difference in the attitude of the participants toward the care of the elderly patients.

Table 2 : t-test analysis of male and female nurses.

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-tab	P
Male	6	3.40	2.62	58	9.59	1.88	0.05
Female	54	22.62	13.52				

In testing the hypothesis, subjects' mean survey was analyzed (male=3.40, female=22.62) with a standard deviation of 2.26 and 13.52 respectively. The data was subjected to t-test analysis and the result was t -calculated=9.59, t -table=1.88 at 0.05 level of significance. The inference is that religion makes a significant difference in the respondents' caring for the elderly patients, so hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Experience on the job will make a significant difference in the participants' caring for the elderly patients.

Table 3 : experience of the participants

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-tab	P
Male	6	2.38	1.20	58	6.15	1.88	0.05
Female	54	12.47	8.54				

The subjects' mean scores were analyzed (male=2.38, female=12.47) with a standard deviation of 1.20 and 8.54 respectively. The t-test was analyzed and result was $t - cal. = 6.15$, $t-tab = 1.88$ at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that experience on the job makes a significant difference in the participants' caring for the elderly patients hence the hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 4: Culture will make a significant difference in the participants' care for the elderly patients

Table 4 : cultural influence on the care of the elderly patients

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-tab	P
Male	6	1.23	1.31	58	3.24	1.88	0.05
Female	54	28.47	3.37				

In testing the hypothesis, the participants' mean scores were analyzed (male=1.33, female=28.47) with standard deviation of 1.31 and 3.37 respectively. Data was subjected to t-test analysis and the result was $t-cal = 3.24$, $t-table = 1.88$ at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that culture makes a significant difference in the participants caring for their elderly patients so the hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSION

Nurses in every specialty need to be conversant with the legal aspects of their practice, and gerontological nurses are no exception. In fact, legal risks may be intensified and legal questions may frequently arise when working in geriatric care settings or while nursing elderly patients. Frequently, gerontological nurses are in highly independent and responsible positions in which they must take decisions without an abundance of professionals with whom to confer, they are often responsible for supervising non-professional staff and ultimately are accountable for the actions of these subordinates. To fully protect themselves, Nurses and their employers must have knowledge of basic laws and ensure that their practice falls within the legally sound boundaries.

Sometimes, elderly abuse can occur in the process of caring for elderly patients either by loved ones, care giving relationships, in which family members or staff burn out, which may be an unfortunate consequence. Abuse can take many forms including inflicting pain or injury, misuse of medications, causing psychological distress, exploiting, confining or withholding food or care, the nurses expanded role today should positively impact on their attitude towards their care of the elderly patients.

Surviving to old age is a tremendous accomplishment. The hurdles of coping with crises, adjusting to changes and learning new skills have been confronted and overcome to varying degrees, throughout their lives, the elderly have faced many important decisions but too often the nurses see the weakness and needs of the elderly so required to initiate interventions to have those needs met from other sources rather than by the elderly themselves, the elderly becomes passive participants in their care, sometimes, it may be difficult for the elderly to accept less involvement in their care, they may become angry or depressed at being forced to forfeit their decision making and functions to others. Unnecessarily, they may develop feeling of dependency, uselessness and powerlessness. It is essential that the nurses recognize the strengths and capabilities of these elderly patients so that they can be partners in, and not just objects of care. Utilizing the resources of the elderly in their own care promotes normally, independence and individuality, it aids in avoiding secondary problems related to the reactions of older adults to an unnecessarily imposed dependent role hence the nurses must have sound knowledge of the ageing process, positive attitude, adequate communication and a better understanding of the needs and problems of these elderly patients in order to render qualitative care.

Harris (1990) suggests that the major role losses associated with old age come with retirement, loss of a partner and institutionalization, and that individuals play a variety of roles throughout their lives which offer them special development leading to status and identity. Nurses that have better understanding of the elderly, experience on the job, sound religious morals will develop positive and enhanced attitude towards the care of the elderly, loving and compassionate tenets of religion teaches love, compassion, care for the elderly, respect of individuality, status and identity, there will be a sense of concern for the other person especially the elderly.

Collins (1992) agreed that knowledge, experience and skills of the carer helps in developing a positive attitude towards the care of the elderly, as there exists a great difference in the gerontological nurses caring for the elderly patients but they concluded that the negative attitude of the non-gerontological nurses reflect those of the society in general which will affect the type and quality of care produced by them for the elderly.

Wilman (1999) asserted that adequate communication with the elderly patients has been the most important aspect of nursing care and that poor communication is the largest source of dissatisfaction in these kinds of patients and that consequently, the quality of care may improve with effective communication. Although, identified were three variables that seem to determine the quality and quantity of nurse-patient communication such as provider, patient and situation variables, that is, the more-educated a nurse, the better in communication skills, nurses' job satisfaction (high levels of intrinsic job motivation), and the nurse who has a better understanding of the prevailing cultural practices of the society where the patients live will be better off in her attitude in caring for the elderly patients as this will help her to interact better with the elderly patients and will impact positively on the patients.

CONCLUSION

There is much defined knowledge and skill for the care of the elderly as in other specialties, gerontology is not an extension of the family health programme hence the need for nurses to be knowledgeable and develop their full potential in the care of elderly patients in the society as the more knowledge and skill acquisition in the care of the elderly the better for a change of attitude toward these special individuals in the communities.

RECOMMENDATION

The researchers made the following recommendations:

- Training programmes on the care of the elderly must be encouraged so that the specialty is better developed for qualitative and quantitative service delivery to the elderly.
- All qualified nurses must be exposed to in-house training on the care of the elderly.
- Clinical psychologists and Social workers should be involved in the care of the elderly patients for improved communication, interaction and rehabilitation.
- Geriatric wards must be created in the hospitals or homes for the aged to be established where the aged can interact with themselves and individualized care rendered.
- Experienced nurses to be posted to the geriatric wards in order to make their experience to bear in the care of the aged.
- Nurses who are religiously committed to their job should be made to work for the elderly to exhibit their religious tenets as this will enhance qualitative nursing care delivery.
- Adequate knowledge of psychosocial/cultural aspects of the elderly by the nurses is crucial to proper management of the elderly so these nurses must update their knowledge for better service delivery.

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